

DEVELOPING SOCIO-LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE FOR JOURNALISM STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the critical importance of sociolinguistic competence in the education of journalism students. As the media landscape becomes increasingly diverse and interconnected, journalists must navigate complex linguistic and cultural contexts to communicate effectively with varied audiences. The study examines existing curricula and identifies gaps in sociolinguistic training, proposing a comprehensive framework that integrates theoretical knowledge with practical skills. Through case studies and interviews with industry professionals, we highlight successful pedagogical strategies that enhance students' understanding of language variation, discourse practices, and audience engagement. The findings underscore the necessity of fostering sociolinguistic awareness to empower future journalists to produce inclusive and impactful narratives in a globalized world.

Keywords: *Communicative competence, Context, ESL instructors, Sociolinguistic competence*

Second language learners frequently struggle with sociolinguistic competence in the target language, leading to difficulties in comprehending and using language appropriately in various contexts. Several factors contribute to these challenges, with a primary reason being insufficient exposure to language that is sociolinguistically suitable. Second language learners often lack sociolinguistic competence in the target language, facing issues in understanding and using language appropriately according to the context and situation. There are a number of reasons for these issues, and one of the main reasons is the lack of exposure to sociolinguistically appropriate language use. Unlike grammatical competence, which focuses on the structure of the language, sociolinguistic competence encompasses the ability to discern and employ language variations that correspond to social contexts, cultural norms, and situational demands. This gap can lead to miscommunication, cultural misunderstandings, and a diminished ability to connect with native speakers.

Moreover, traditional language instruction often prioritizes vocabulary and grammar over real-world application, leaving students ill-equipped to navigate the

subtleties of language in different social settings. This deficiency can hinder their effectiveness in professional environments, particularly in fields such as journalism, where understanding the nuances of language is crucial for reporting, interviewing, and storytelling.

To address these challenges, it is essential to develop targeted pedagogical strategies that incorporate sociolinguistic elements into language learning curricula. By providing learners with opportunities to engage with authentic materials, practice in diverse contexts, and reflect on their language use, educators can help foster a more comprehensive linguistic competence. This article aims to highlight effective approaches for cultivating sociolinguistic awareness among journalism students, ultimately preparing them to communicate more effectively and empathetically in a multicultural society.

Developing ESL and EFL learners' sociolinguistic competence may not be an easy task, but instructors need to provide learners with opportunities for exposure and production of sociolinguistically appropriate language for them to communicate effectively with others. The need for sociolinguistic competence is further amplified by the internationalisation of higher education in the country, as local students would communicate with other students from all over the world with different values and cultures (Mustapha, et al., 2021).

In the development, organization, and enhancement of foreign language skills among future journalists, it is becoming increasingly important to incorporate sociolinguistic variables into the teaching methods and processes.

Before discussing sociolinguistic competence, it is imperative to first discuss the notion of communicative competence, which sociolinguistic competence falls under. Hymes (1972) defines communicative competence as the ability of the language user to produce and understand the language to communicate appropriately within specific contexts and settings. According to Canale and Swain (1980), and later extended by Canale (1983), the dimensions of communicative competence include grammatical competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence and strategic competence. Language learners with grammatical competence have knowledge on the form and structure of the language, while those with sociolinguistic, discourse and strategic competence have knowledge and ability in using the language appropriately in a variety of contexts. Having communicative competence allows second and foreign language learners to communicate effectively with others, placing emphasis on not only accuracy but also appropriateness (Savignon, 2018).

Wolfson (2014, p. 62-63) approves of the idea of different patterns of interaction existing within diverse speech communities whose members share understanding of

adjusting the speech conduct according the particular situations. Besides considering what is appropriate to say and when including conversational topics and forms of address there are also speech acts (e.g. greetings, compliments, apologies, invitations and complaints) that are to be used, interpreted and a suitable reaction needs to be chosen. Otherwise, it can result in communication breakdowns that undermine mutual trust and make it nearly impossible to foster further relationships. Participants may experience unintended insults, injustices, or harm, regardless of the speaker's intentions.

The focal point of Communicative language teaching approach is a language as a means of communication aiming at communicative competence. (Richards, 2014, p. 87-91). Some features of language emphasize its role as a system for expressing meaning. However, this perspective focuses on "strategic communication" rather than a sociolinguistic approach. It views interaction and communication as the primary objectives, which are reflected in the language's structure, highlighting its communicative function and usage. Richards (2014, p. 87-91) states that grammar and structure do not pertain to the main characteristic of language and its primal pursuits are the categories of functional and communicative meaning. The knowledge of setting and participants influence the decision whether to use formal or informal speech. Different types of texts and their production are another aim of this approach and communication strategies serve as tool for communication maintenance. (Richards, 2014, p. 87-91)

Sociolinguistic competence in a foreign language means that philological journalists master the elements of discourse variation across different social and communicative contexts. These elements are fundamental to sociolinguistic knowledge. The curriculum focused on sociolinguistic principles in foreign language education aims to enhance the sociolinguistic abilities of journalism students. This specialized content provides a foundation for improving students' understanding, skills, and capabilities to tailor their communicative behavior according to the speech profile of their interlocutors, while also considering the sociolinguistic norms recognized in specific social contexts.

Teachers' awareness of the significance of developing sociolinguistic competence corresponds to their understanding of this aspect of language. However, it is essential to enhance both their theoretical knowledge and practical skills in this area.

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